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Research Article

**INCIDENCE OF HYDROCEPHALUS IN TUBERCULOUS
MENINGITIS PATIENTS**¹Dr. Muhammad Riaz, ¹Dr. Alam Zeb, ²Dr. Zara Babar¹Pakistan Institute of Medical Sciences (PIMS), Islamabad²DHQ Hospital Nankana Sahib**Abstract:**

Tuberculous meningitis is one of the serious health concern in underdeveloped as well as in developing countries as it results in significant mortality and morbidity for life. On an estimate 20 out of 1M people die of disease in Asia per year. This disease may lead to significant complications i.e. paraplegia, paralysis, hydrocephalus, Neurological deficit and lifelong disability.

***Object:** The study was designed to determine the incidence of TBM patients presenting Pakistan Institute of Medical Sciences Islamabad (PIMS).*

***Setting and Method:** The method of study was cross-sectional.*

***Place and Duration:** The study was carried out in Pakistan Institute of Medical Sciences Islamabad (PIMS) from June 2017 to June 2018.*

***Results:** 220 patients who fulfilled the criteria were included in the study 132 were males and 88 were females, mean age was 37.31 ± 12.92 years. Hydrocephalus was seen in 65.46% of cases and it has high incidence in male population as compared to female population i.e. 75.75% as compared to 55.68%. The age groups 25 to 40 were maximally affected by the complication of hydrocephalus i.e. 70.8% of patients of the mentioned age group suffered from Hydrocephalus. 9/11 Patients suffered from stage I TBM whereas 51/72 affected by stage II suffered from Hydrocephalus.*

***Conclusion:** Patients who suffer from TBM are on high risk to develop hydrocephalus and the risk is significantly higher in male gender. The detailed demographic data was taken and patients fulfilling the inclusion criteria of TBM underwent CT Brain with IV-Contrast for confirmation of the disease.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Tuberculosis is an ominous disease having high

incidence in underdeveloped and developing world. Tuberculosis is primarily the disease of Respiratory system but it can be spread to any part of body that may be brain, bones or meninges. It is of major concern as it has high infectivity due to droplet spread. The incidence of T.B is really high in developing and underdeveloped countries and it has now reemergence in developed countries due to rise in the number of HIV infections as HIV patients are highly susceptible to the T.B. The incidence of T.B in Pakistan is 276/100000 population. With the now advancement of the technology, certain molecular diagnostic technologies are developed but for T.B the main dependence is still on microbiological diagnosis of Acid Fast Bacilli and the result may take a few weeks to develop thereby delaying diagnosis and management. T.B.M as an entity is a highly destructive as even with the treatment continuation of ATT. It could result in mortality or lifelong morbidity of the patient. Drug resistance and new strains of T.B plays vital role in it. The TBM develops in two step mechanism, Mycobacterium Tuberculosis enters the body by droplet infection then infects the lung parenchyma and then spreads to the lymph nodes of the region forming primary complex, then it disseminates to the whole body e.g to meninges forming rich Foci which may then rupture into subarachnoid space causing meningitis or form small Foci in subpial or sub ependymal areas forming tuberculoma and causing encephalitis.

The presentation of the TBM can be fever, headache, weight loss, vomiting, photophobia, cranial nerve palsies and unconsciousness. The change in level of consciousness is classified by British Medical Research Council into three stages, Furthermore, TBM can be complicated and result into seizure disorder, hearing loss and hydrocephalus. TBM has high chances of complications due to less sensitivity of drugs and emerging resistance in AFB. The incidence of TBM can vary from area to area as the incidence and cases of T.B varies. A study was done in PIMS Hospital shows, out of 150 patients of TBM who presented in stage I and stage II of BMRC, 90 patients developed hydrocephalus. In another study done in Karachi, it was shown that 61% of total TBM patients developed hydrocephalus. In this study, the data is presented of the cases who presented in Pakistan Institute of Medical Sciences (PIMS) Islamabad, and the aim is to compare the results of the study to the other studies done in different parts of the world.

METHODS AND MATERIALS:

The study was done at the Pakistan Institute of

Medical Sciences (PIMS) Islamabad from June 2017 to June 2018. Preformed Performa's were used to take informed consent by the conscious patients themselves and from the guardian/attendant of the patient having blood relation in case of unconsciousness of the patient. Patients who fulfilled the criteria were included in the study. All demographic details were noted gender, sex, age etc, analyzed and recorded. Criteria for inclusion: Age 16-55 years and diagnosed as T.B.M. Criteria for exclusion: Age less than 16 and more than 55 years' patients having structural Brain Lesion, Meningitis other than T.B.M. patients having Cyst or Tumor in Brain. Hx of head Trauma in past one year. Bleeding diathesis. Platelets less 50,000/mm³

CRITERIA FOR DIAGNOSIS: Patient having any of the following lab data and any two or more of the clinical features is diagnosed as a case of TBM.

CLINICAL FACTOR

1. Patients having more than 99°F fever for 6 hours per day for at least 14 days.
2. Dull Persisting headache, 3hours/day for a week or more.
3. History of vomiting minimum 3 times a day for at least 3 days,
4. Hx of T.B in family (T.B contact in last 2 years)

LABORATORY FINDINGS

1. CSF smears positive for AFB isolated on fluorescence staining of CSF.
2. CSF culture positive for AFB mycobacterium Tuberculosis isolated after growth on Bactec media this takes 4-6 weeks.
3. Lymphocytic Pleocytosis: Microscopic pictures of CSF show 20-500 Lymphocytes /mm³, Protein about 100/mm³ and Glucose 60-65% of the corresponding level in plasma. BMRC criteria for TBM.

There are 3 stages. Stage I, GCS 15/15, oriented, alert and no focal deficit. Stage II, GCS 11-14, or 15 oriented, alert but with focal deficit. Stage III, GCS 10 or less than 10, with or without focal deficit.

HYDROCEPHALUS

A Patient is labelled as a case of hydrocephalus when any of the ventricles were dilated lateral, 3rd or 4th, by 25% of the normal value on CT Brain Plain by a consultant Radiologist.

RESULTS:

The calculated data was analyzed with the help of

SPSS 21. The quantitative variables like weight and age were taken as mean. Percentages and frequencies were taken for age group, gender and TBM stage. Stratification of effect modifiers were done and Chi-square was taken post stratification where $P > 0.05$.

Results: Out of 220 cases 132 were males and 88 were females with mean age 37.31 ± 12.92 years were labelled as cases of Hydrocephalus. The proportion of the males is higher as compared to

females and the age group 31-40 years had most no. of cases. The highest percentage of the patients who were labelled as Hydrocephalus had stage I TBM i.e. 9/11 (81.8), whereas 22/31 (70.9) % patients of stage II cases had Hydrocephalus and the percentage is minimum in stage III disease i.e. (47%).

Table 1: Gender Hydrocephalus

Gender	Yes	No
Male	100/132 (75.75%)	32/132 (24.24)
Female	48/88 (54.54%)	40/88 (45.45)
Total	148/220 (67.27%)	72/220 (32.73%)

Table 2: Age groups

Age Group	Yes	No
16-30	53/91 (58.24%)	38/91 (41.75%)
31-40	22/31 (70.96%)	9/31 (29.03%)
41-55	57/96 (59.37%)	39/96 (40.62%)
Total	132/218	86/218

Table 3. Stages of TBM

Stage	Yes	No
I	9/11 (81.81%)	2/11 (18.18%)
II	51/72 (70.83%)	21/72 (29.16%)
III	8/17 (47.05%)	9/17 (52.95%)
Total	68/100	32/100

DISCUSSION:

Hydrocephalus was seen in 65.46% of cases. The result of this study is comparable with another study done by Thwaite's GE, the result of that study showed that the TBM patients who suffered from Hydrocephalus are 68% of total TBM patients. The result of our study is lower as compared to this one. This may be because of cut off values, age window and change of inclusion criteria. similar results were seen in a study done by Nabi S and khattak S in which it was noted to be 60%. A much higher percentage of males was seen in a study done by Kumar R and Christensen but it could not be associated with any reason significantly. In our study the percentage of males is higher than females, this may be due to that most of the males presented in stage II of TBM and it had the highest percentage of

Hydrocephalus cases. The age group 25-40 was observed to be more affected by the TBM then age group 41-50 and age group of more than 50 years.

The result is in accordance with a study done by Hosuglu S and Geyik MF in Turkey but a strong correlation cannot be made that why this age group is more affected than the other age groups. Most number of cases of hydrocephalus were seen in stage II in our study but the results are similar with a study done at Civil Hospital Karachi by Salekeen S in which the maximum number of patients presented were in stage II according to BMRC criteria. And another study by Chan KH showed 89% of cases of tuberculous meningitis who developed hydrocephalus were in stage II and stage III. This reaffirms our belief that as the disease progresses chances of

developing hydrocephalus increases.

CONCLUSION:

Tuberculous meningitis is a highly morbid and mortal disease posing threat to the public health in our country. Hydrocephalus, as a complication of this disease, has high association of occurrence with male gender.

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